

Prevalence and Antimicrobial Resistance of *Escherichia Coli* Isolated from Slaughterhouses in Can Tho and An Giang Provinces, Vietnam

Danh Thi Thuy Trang¹, Pham Nguyen Vu², Ngo Văn Thong^{3*}

^{1,2,3}Faculty of Agriculture and Rural Development, Kien Giang University

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7369-2357>

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ABSTRACT

Slaughterhouses are critical interfaces for the transmission of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria between animals, humans, and the environment. This study investigated the prevalence, antimicrobial resistance, and multidrug resistance (MDR) of *Escherichia coli* isolated from slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. A total of 72 samples, including feces (n = 48), wastewater (n = 8), and floor swabs (n = 16), were collected from the Can Tho and An Giang provinces. Isolation and identification were performed using standard microbiological methods, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing was conducted using the disk diffusion method following CLSI guidelines. The prevalence of *E. coli* was 77.03% in fecal samples, 37.50% in wastewater, and 50.00% in floor swabs, with significantly higher rates in An Giang (p < 0.05). High resistance was observed for streptomycin (79.31–89.83%) and ampicillin (51.72–86.44%), while resistance to colistin remained low (≤6.90%). Overall, 87.6% of isolates were multidrug-resistant. These findings highlight the widespread occurrence of antimicrobial-resistant *E. coli* in slaughterhouse environments and emphasize the need for improved hygiene and prudent antimicrobial use to mitigate public health risks.

Corresponding Author:
Ngo Van Thong

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1. INTRODUCTION

Escherichia coli is a commensal bacterium widely present in the intestinal tract of animals and humans and is commonly used as an indicator organism for fecal contamination and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance (Nhung et al., 2017; WHO, 2022). The rapid emergence of antimicrobial-resistant and multidrug-resistant (MDR) *E. coli* has become a major global health concern (Prestinaci et al., 2015).

The extensive use of antibiotics in livestock production is considered a primary driver of AMR, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where antimicrobial usage is often poorly regulated (Van Boeckel et al., 2015). In Vietnam, antibiotics are frequently used for both therapeutic and prophylactic purposes, contributing to the selection of resistant bacterial strains (Nhung et al., 2017).

Slaughterhouses represent critical control points for the dissemination of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria into the food chain and environment. Contamination may occur through feces, wastewater, equipment, and contact surfaces during slaughtering processes (Nastasijevec et al., 2017). Previous studies have demonstrated that slaughterhouse environments can act as reservoirs of resistant bacteria (Trung et al., 2021).

Despite increasing concerns, data on *E. coli* contamination and resistance patterns in slaughterhouses in the Mekong Delta remain limited. Therefore, this study aimed to (i) determine the prevalence of *E. coli* in different sample types and (ii) evaluate antimicrobial resistance and multidrug resistance patterns in isolates from Can Tho and An Giang provinces.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Design, Site and Time

A cross-sectional study was conducted at selected slaughterhouses in Can Tho and An Giang provinces (Mekong Delta, Vietnam). Sampling was carried out from December 2025 to April 2026. These facilities represent typical small- to medium-scale pig and poultry processing operations under normal commercial conditions.

2.2. Sample Size and Sampling Strategy

A total of 72 samples were collected, including feces (n = 48), wastewater (n = 8), and slaughterhouse floor cleaning samples (n = 16). Samples were distributed proportionally among provinces based on facility output.

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2.3. Sample Collection and Transportation

Stool samples were collected directly from the rectum using a sterile swab, then preserved in a Cary-Blair Medium, labeled, and stored at 4–8 °C for transport to the laboratory for *E. coli* isolation within 24 hours. Surface samples were collected using a sterile swab pre-moistened with buffered peptone (BPW), sampling a defined area (~10 cm²) in a standard zigzag pattern. Wastewater samples from the slaughterhouse were collected according to the National Technical Regulation on Livestock Wastewater (QCVN 62-MT:2016/BTNMT), Vietnamese Standard TCVN 5999:1995 (ISO 5667/10: 1992) on water quality - sampling - guidelines for wastewater sampling. All samples were kept in insulated coolers (2–8°C) and transported to the laboratory within 6–8 hours for immediate processing.

2.4. Isolation and Identification of *E. coli*

Samples were pre-enriched in BPW (ratio 1:9 w/v for feces; 10 mL wastewater into 90 mL BPW; swabs were dipped in 10 mL BPW) and incubated at 37 °C for 18–24 hours. A loop of inoculated material was spread evenly onto Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar, then incubated at 37 °C for 18–24 hours. Suspected *E. coli* colonies (metallic blue colonies on EMB medium) was subcultured for purity testing. Confirmation was performed using standard biochemical assays (IMViC: Indole +, Methyl Red +, Voges–Proskauer –, Citrate –).

2.5. Antibiotic Sensitivity Test (AST)

A total of 88 *E. coli* strains were isolated from 48 positive samples. AST was performed using the Mueller–Hinton agar plate diffusion method according to CLSI guidelines (latest version). The bacterial suspension is adjusted to the 0.5 McFarland standard and spread evenly onto the agar plates. Antibiotic discs (Oxoid or equivalent) included: streptomycin (10 µg), ampicillin (10 µg), enrofloxacin (5 µg), florfenicol

(30 µg), colistin (10 µg), and doxycycline (30 µg). Plates were incubated at 35–37 °C for 16–18 hours. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured and interpreted as susceptible, intermediate, or resistant according to CLSI thresholds. For analysis, intermediate isolates were categorized as resistant.

Quality control was performed using *E. coli* ATCC 25922 to ensure the accuracy of AST results.

2.6. Data management and statistical analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using statistical software (e.g., SPSS 2016). Prevalence was calculated as the proportion of positive samples. Differences in prevalence between provinces and sample types were assessed using the Chi-square or Fisher’s exact test where appropriate. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize resistance profiles, and MDR patterns were tabulated.

2.7. Biosafety and ethical considerations

All laboratory procedures were conducted following institutional biosafety guidelines for handling potentially pathogenic bacteria. Sampling was non-invasive and did not involve live animal experimentation; therefore, formal ethical approval was not required under local regulations.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Prevalence of *E. coli*

The prevalence of *E. coli* was highest in fecal samples (77.03%), followed by slaughter floor swabs (50%) and wastewater samples (37.50%). A significantly higher prevalence was observed in An Giang compared to Can Tho for fecal and wastewater samples (p < 0.05), while no significant difference was observed for floor swabs (p > 0.05). Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Prevalence of *E. coli* in samples

Location	Stool sample			Wastewater sample			Slaughterhouse floor swab sample		
	No.	positive	%	No.	positive	%	No.	positive	%
Can Tho	24	16	66.67	4	1	25	8	4	50
An Giang	24	21	87.50	4	2	50	8	4	50
P			<0.05			<0.05			>0,05
Total	48	37	77.03	8	3	37.50	16	8	50

3.2. Antimicrobial resistance profiles

High sensitive rates were observed for several antibiotics: Colistin: 93.10–93.22%, Doxycycline: 74.58–82.76%, Enrofloxacin: 72.41–93.22%. Moderate resistance was found

for ampicillin and florfenicol, while High resistance was observed for streptomycin. Isolates from An Giang showed generally higher resistance rates. The results are shown in Table 2

Table 2: Antibiotic resistance rate of *E. coli*

Antibiotic	Can Tho (n= 29)				An Giang (n= 59)			
	Sensitive	(%)	Resistance	(%)	Sensitive	(%)	Resistance	(%)
Aminoglycoside	6	20,69	23	79,31	6	10,17	53	89,83

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Streptomycin								
Beta-lactam	14	48,28	15	51,72	8	13,56	51	86,44
Ampicillin								
Quinolone	21	72,41	8	27,59	55	93,22	4	6,78
Enrofloxacin								
Phenicol	15	51,72	14	48,28	17	28,81	42	71,19
Florfenicol								
Polymyxin	27	93,10	2	6,90	55	93,22	4	6,78
Colistin								
Tetracycline	24	82,76	5	17,24	44	74,58	15	25,42
Doxycycline								

3.3. Multidrug resistance patterns

Out of 88 isolates, 77 (87.6%) were multidrug-resistant. Resistance to three antibiotics was the most common pattern

(31.82%). Some isolates exhibited resistance to up to five antibiotics. The results are shown in Table 3

Table 3: The level of multidrug resistance in E. coli strains isolated at the slaughterhouse.

Number of antibiotics	Number of isolated strains	Number of phenotypes	Phenotype	percentage (%)
0	11			
		8	Am	9,09
1	14	1	Co	1,14
		2	Fl	2,27
		3	Sm	3,41
		1	Am+Dx	1,14
		3	Co+Dx	3,41
2	21	1	Ef+Am	1,14
		11	Fl+Am	12,50
		1	Sm+Dx	1,14
		2	Sm+Am	2,27
		2	Sm+Ef	2,27
		1	Ef+Fl+Co	1,14
3	34	1	Fl+Am+Dx	1,14
		28	Sm+Fl+Am	31,82
		1	Sm+Ef+Dx	1,14
		3	Sm+Ef+Am	3,41
		1	Sm+Fl+Am+Dx	1,14
4	7	3	Sm+Fl+Am+Co	3,41
		1	Sm+Ef+Am+Co	1,14
		2	Sm+Ef+Fl+Am	2,27
5	1	1	Sm+Fl+Am+Co+Dx	1,14
	88	77		87,6

Am: ampicillin; Sm: streptomycin; Ef: enrofloxacin; Fl: florfenicol; Co: colistin; Dx: doxycycline

4. DISCUSSION

The present study revealed a high prevalence of Escherichia coli in slaughterhouse environments, particularly in fecal samples (77.03%), followed by floor swabs (50.00%) and wastewater (37.50%). These findings are consistent with previous studies in Vietnam and Southeast Asia, where E. coli prevalence in livestock and slaughterhouse environments typically ranges from 50% to over 90% (Nguyen et al., 2015; Bui et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2023). The high detection rate

in feces confirms the role of E. coli as a key indicator organism for fecal contamination and hygiene status in animal production systems (Marshall & Levy, 2011; EFSA, 2021).

The significantly higher prevalence observed in An Giang compared to Can Tho suggests potential differences in slaughterhouse hygiene, biosecurity measures, and animal handling practices. Similar regional variations have been reported in Vietnam, where smallholder and semi-industrial

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systems often lack standardized sanitation protocols (Nhung et al., 2016; Carrique-Mas & Rushton, 2017). In addition, the presence of *E. coli* in wastewater and on slaughterhouse surfaces highlights the importance of environmental reservoirs in maintaining and disseminating bacterial contamination, as also documented in previous environmental surveillance studies (Le et al., 2015; Hoang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2009).

The antimicrobial resistance patterns observed in this study are particularly concerning. High resistance rates to streptomycin and ampicillin (up to 89.83% and 86.44%, respectively) are in agreement with numerous reports from Vietnam and other developing countries (Nguyen et al., 2016; Khanh et al., 2017; Trung et al., 2021). These antibiotics have been widely used for decades in livestock production, often without strict regulation, leading to strong selective pressure and the emergence of resistant strains (Van Boeckel et al., 2015; Laxminarayan et al., 2013). In Vietnam, antimicrobial use in animal production accounts for a large proportion of total antibiotic consumption, further exacerbating the AMR problem (Carrique-Mas et al., 2020; Nhung et al., 2016).

Resistance to florfenicol was also notably high, especially in An Giang (71.19%), suggesting frequent usage in veterinary practice. This finding is consistent with reports indicating that phenicol resistance is increasingly common due to co-selection mechanisms and the presence of mobile genetic elements carrying multiple resistance genes (Dang et al., 2020; Pham et al., 2022). In contrast, the relatively low resistance to colistin ($\leq 6.90\%$) observed in this study is encouraging, given its critical importance as a last-resort antibiotic in human medicine (Rhouma et al., 2016; WHO, 2017). However, previous studies in Vietnam have reported the emergence of colistin resistance genes such as *mcr-1*, emphasizing the need for continuous monitoring (Trung et al., 2021; Pham et al., 2015).

The high susceptibility to enrofloxacin, particularly in An Giang, contrasts with global trends showing increasing resistance to fluoroquinolones (Tang et al., 2017; Holmes et al., 2016). This discrepancy may reflect differences in antibiotic usage patterns or local regulatory practices. Nevertheless, resistance to critically important antimicrobials remains a growing concern, as these drugs are essential for treating severe infections in humans (WHO, 2021; Aidara-Kane et al., 2018).

A key finding of this study is the very high prevalence of multidrug resistance (MDR), detected in 87.6% of *E. coli* isolates. This rate is comparable to or even higher than those reported in other studies in Vietnam and Southeast Asia, where MDR prevalence often exceeds 70–90% (Pham et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2023). The predominance of resistance to three or more antibiotics suggests the role of co-selection and horizontal gene transfer in the dissemination of resistance (Holmes et al., 2016; Silbergeld et al., 2008). Indeed, previous studies have identified multiple resistance genes

such as *bla*TEM, *tetA*, and *sul1* in *E. coli* isolates from livestock and slaughterhouse environments (Dang et al., 2020; Le et al., 2018).

The presence of MDR *E. coli* in slaughterhouses raises serious concerns for food safety and public health. Slaughterhouses act as critical control points where bacteria from animals, humans, and the environment can interact and spread along the food chain (Marshall & Levy, 2011; Zurfluh et al., 2015). Several studies have demonstrated the transmission of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria from food animals to humans via contaminated meat products (Prestinaci et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2017). In Vietnam, the detection of antimicrobial-resistant *E. coli* in both livestock and farm workers further supports the zoonotic potential of these pathogens (Nguyen et al., 2015; Trung et al., 2021).

At a broader level, Vietnam has been recognized as a hotspot for antimicrobial resistance due to high antimicrobial usage, rapid intensification of livestock production, and limited regulatory enforcement (Carrique-Mas et al., 2020; O'Neill, 2016). Although national action plans have been implemented to reduce antimicrobial use and strengthen surveillance, challenges remain, particularly in small-scale farming systems where antibiotics are easily accessible and frequently used without veterinary oversight (FAO, 2016; WOA, 2020).

The findings of this study highlight the urgent need for integrated interventions based on the One Health approach. Improving slaughterhouse hygiene, strengthening biosecurity measures, and promoting prudent antimicrobial use are essential strategies to reduce the spread of resistant bacteria (Aidara-Kane et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2017). In addition, routine surveillance of antimicrobial resistance in slaughterhouse environments should be enhanced to provide early warning of emerging resistance trends.

Finally, some limitations of this study should be acknowledged. The sample size was relatively limited, and molecular characterization of resistance genes was not performed. Future studies should incorporate genomic approaches to better understand resistance mechanisms and transmission dynamics of MDR *E. coli* in the food production chain (Holmes et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2009).

5. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates a high prevalence of *E. coli* and widespread antimicrobial resistance in slaughterhouse environments in the Mekong Delta. The high MDR rate (87.6%) and low resistance to colistin, which remains a critically important antibiotic

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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